

CONTEMPORARY TECHNIQUES FOR TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract: *The article deals with one of the top questions of today concerning the activity of modern foreign language course should consist of. Education's goals and content are changing, and new teaching methods and technologies are rising, yet no matter what changes are implemented, teaching remains the internal and primary form of learning. Whatever innovations are implemented, participants in the educational process only meet at the lesson: educator and learner. Today, the purpose of teaching a foreign language is not merely imparting a particular quantity of content that individuals must memorize and replicate. Simultaneously with the armament of information and its foundation, it is vital to teach students the modes of cognition and practical activity produced by society.*

Keywords: *teaching foreign language, CLT, CEFR, GTM, technology, communicative competency.*

According to the educational standard, the objective of teaching foreign languages is presented to develop students' foreign-language communicative capacity for functioning in a multicultural environment in everyday, professional, and scientific fields. In 2012, Uzbekistan adopted the Common European Framework of Reference (CEFR) as a framework for teaching, studying, and assessing languages. CLT (Communicative Language Teaching) is used inside the CEFR, and the approach is very different from the rule-based/grammar-translation method (GTM) to language instruction that the Uzbek language instructors are used to. A language teacher's identity in CLT is that of a facilitator rather than a conduit of information. Learning languages for communicative reasons transfers the attention of the classroom from the teacher to the student; yet, this change does not imply that the teacher has no role to perform. The role of a teacher is to help learners to become communicatively competent in four areas: linguistic, sociolinguistic, pragmatic, and strategic. This section will address

communicative competencies and propose interactive classroom activities for teaching foreign languages within the CEFR framework.

As a result, it is believed that the lesson will take place in an environment in which students communicate with one another and organize group discussions on the topic. The pupils' voices are heard more than the teacher's in this scenario. Take, for example, the following sentence explanation:

The sister (she) of my friend (he), sitting in front of me, is the best.

The teacher instructs the students to debate for two minutes whether he or she is sitting. where some pupils respond that he is sitting and others that she is. Furthermore, the teacher would inquire as to why some students made the decisions they did. The class debates but does not reach an agreement. Does the teacher inquire whether any syntactical rules would ensure his or her sitting? If no student can provide an exact solution to the presented question.

This example demonstrates that syntactic rules alone are insufficient to solve the previous query. Language is about social context or the real-world context into which syntactic rules should fit into, not the other way around. People may make GTM errors while communicating, but they may be correct from a communication standpoint. GTM says that "friend/he" is sitting because "there is at least a collocational relationship between "friend/he" and "sitting" in which sitting in front of me is a phrase headed by the participle.

To explain how non-linguistic variables influence how we interpret words, sentences, and so on, the teacher uses another example:

Wait for me for 10 minutes.

The teacher resumes the preceding conversation by asking participants whether they believe this statement was successful or not. Students generally report that they understand what is being said and that the intended meaning is clear. However, the trainer explains that the situation between two persons in real life is not successful. because the speaker's interculture does not perceive the remark adequately from a cultural standpoint The widening circle of Englishes is portrayed as a particular period, but not the real ten minutes, in the social context for this statement. Even while ten minutes is an objective truth, different cultures influence how we view it. Thus, we must determine whether to educate students to be competent just in knowing facts and regulations or to be competent in putting these facts and rules into practice. A communicative aim should be accomplished.

Conclusion. There are numerous approaches and methods for teaching and learning languages. CLT has grown in popularity in Uzbekistan during the

previous decade. This phrase is closely related to the CEFR. CLT is intimately related to learning through practice and real-life settings in which every aspect of the language is tested. Exploring the world by verbal communication and clarifying in writing. Teachers shouldn't consider language education to be a content area of expertise. To sum up, language is a tool for genuine communication rather than a subject to be studied.

REFERENCES:

1. Bax, S. Putting technology in its place: ICT in modern Foreign language teaching.
2. Chiesa D.L., Azizov U., Khan S., Nazmutdinova K., Tangirova K. Reconceptualizing Language teaching: and in-service in Uzbekistan. Baktaria, 2019.
3. Richards, C. & Rodgers, T.S. Approaches and methods in language teaching. Cambridge: Cambridge Press, 2014.
4. Ахмедова Л.Т., Лагай Е.А. Современные технологии преподавания русского языка и литературы. Ташкент, 2016
5. Дьюи Дж. Современные подходы в обучении современным языкам.